

gr. iv. M. Pulveres tales, viij. To take one every half-hour until repeated vomiting has been produced.—*Hufeland and Osann's Journal*, B. 81. Juli, 1835.

On Hæmorrhagic Pericarditis. By Dr. SEIDLITZ, Senior Physician to the Naval Hospital at St. Petersburg.

[THE memoir, of which we here present the reader with an abstract, occupies sixty pages of the last number which has reached us of Dr. Hecker's *Annalen*, and possesses extraordinary interest, as well from the pathological character of its details as from their novelty. We have been as much influenced by a feeling of convenience in adopting the name given above to this affection, as by any strong opinion of its superiority to that employed by our author. In his memoir, Dr. Seidlitz terms the disease *Pericarditis exsudatoria sanguinolenta*. Although we have greatly condensed the whole paper, we believe we have given all that is really important in it of a pathological and therapeutical character; but we have omitted much interesting discussion, in which the author attempts to prove the identity of the disease with the *Morbus cardiacus* of the ancients. For this we must refer the reader to the original article, and to the 31st, 32d, and 37th chapters of Cælius Aurelianus, wherein he treats of the *Morbus cardiacus*, or *Cardiaca passio*. We shall only be able to afford room for a small portion of Dr. Seidlitz's extracts from the ancient author.]

In 1831, several sailors died suddenly at St. Petersburg, whilst engaged at work; others who were admitted at the hospital survived only during a short period. On their bodies being examined by Dr. Seidlitz, it appeared that their death was owing to a severe inflammation of the pericardium, joined to a copious exudation of a sanguineous fluid into the pericardial sac. On his communicating the facts, and exhibiting some of the diseased hearts to the association of German physicians (at St. P.) Dr. Crichton remarked that the disease (which he designated as acute hydropericardia) was one of frequent occurrence amongst the troops. The symptoms were too characteristic to be overlooked on the re-appearance of the disease, and thus Dr. S. was subsequently enabled to treat it with success in its earlier stages, or to verify his diagnosis by cadaveric inspection in the cases which terminated fatally. He characterized the disease as "pericarditis exsudatoria sanguinolenta in homine scorbuto affecto." Its pathological features differed in many respects from those commonly attributed to pericarditis, and it appeared to Dr. S. as a new and peculiar disease. On referring, however, to the description of the *morbus cardiacus* by Cælius Aurelianus, he became at once convinced of the identity of the last-named disorder with the one he had to treat.

The number of fatal cases of this disease recorded in the hospital books, between March 1831 and September 1834, is stated at fifteen; that of those which terminated favorably was more considerable. Of these cases the majority occurred in February 1832, when the disorder appears to have assumed an epidemic character. It is remarkable that the complaint was only to be met with between the months of February and September; the period during which scorbutic forms of disease commonly prevail at St. Petersburg; and it was usually associated with a transitory epidemic of a rheumatic nature, while pleurisy was commonly prevalent at the same moment. Thus, perhaps, the scorbutic constitution, or epidemic tendency to scorbutus, might be considered as the predisposing, the *rheumatic* as the occasional cause of the malady. The disposition to sanguineous exudation from the pericardium was rendered the more evident during those periods, by the fact, that in persons who had died of quite dissimilar complaints, the small quantity of fluid contained in the pericardium had assumed the colour of blood.

Case.—Towards the end of February (1831), a sailor, aged 27, of a muscular habit, was seized with an unusual degree of lassitude after a hard day's work. A peculiar sense of anxiety caused him repeatedly to start out of an unrefreshing slumber. Tightness of the chest ensued on the following day. The præcordia seemed the primary seat of distress, from whence an obtuse pain radiated over the whole anterior surface of the thorax, and centered itself on the second day (that of his admittance at the hospital) in the right hypochondriac region. Both these

places were impatient of touch, which without precisely causing pain, seemed to the patient to impede his breathing. The countenance was bloated, of a bilious hue. The breathing was regular, but superficial; deep and full when the patient exerted himself, and attended by neither pain nor cough. Pulse very frequent, and very indistinct (suppressed, unterdrückt). Pulsation of the heart imperceptible to the hand, and scarcely audible. The patient was perfectly conscious, but morose and torpid, preferring to lie flat on his back or on his left side, and with his head low. He denied having been attacked with rigors or with febrile heat. V.S. ad lb. iss. Blood buffed, yielding a large proportion of serum. A solution of nitrate of potash with tartarized antimony, and saline clysmata, were administered. The latter produced several stools. The night was passed more tranquilly, although but with little sleep. The pulse had now become less frequent and more developed, but the pulsation of the heart was more indistinct. The countenance was expressive of great anxiety, but still nothing was complained of but an entire prostration of strength. The temperature of the skin underwent frequent changes from moderate warmth to a marble-like coldness, accompanied by a cold sweat. Action of the kidneys regular. Four cupping-glasses were applied to the region of the liver, and the saline potion and clysmata repeated. On the morning of the fourth day, the patient's apathy had increased: alternately groaning and sighing, he evinced a great dislike to be interrogated. Pulsation, both of the heart and arteries, was no longer distinguishable; the lips were blue; face and extremities of a marble-like coldness. Whilst Dr. S. was in the act of examining the abdomen, the patient suddenly applied his left hand to his head, then to his chest, stretched his eyelids wide asunder, and expired. In the next moment the pupils became strongly dilated. An incision was instantly made into the swollen jugular veins, from which the blood issued in a small stream. Respiration was at the same time artificially sustained by alternately compressing the thorax, and again allowing it to expand, but in vain.

On the thorax being opened, the eye was struck with the extraordinary size of the pericardium, and with its livid appearance, owing to the translucent fluid wherewith it was distended. An incision being made into this membrane, from four to five pounds of fluid escaped, having the colour of dark venous blood and the consistency of a decoction of marsh-mallows. The entire absence of crassamentum disproved this fluid to be genuine blood, whilst the fact of its coagulating through the influence of heat, showed it to consist of the albuminous serum mixed with the colouring matter of the blood. The inner surface of the pericardium was tinged of a dark blue red, and lined with a coat of villous, granular fibres, of the same colour, which lining was easily separated from the pericardium, and had rather the character of a deposit from the fluid than of the false membranes which attach themselves to the pleura in exudatory inflammation of the latter membrane. On removing the above fibrous layer, the envelope of the heart appeared of the same blue red colour; its surface smooth, shining, and sound. The substance of the heart itself was dark red and very firm. The compression by the extravasated fluid had reduced the volume of the heart to the size of a man's fist, and its four cavities to a mere nothing. The abdominal organs were healthy, although the veins were here, as well as in the thoracic cavity, gorged with blood.

The author proceeds to contrast the characteristics of the above case with those of genuine pericarditis, as well the acute as chronic, from both of which its phenomena differ conspicuously, during life and after death. Had the inflammation a scorbutic character? The discoloured state of the heart and pericardium, together with the scorbutic appearance and the rapid collection of the exuded fluid, render it probable. Nor is it disproved by the absence of some of the external attributes of this disease, for it is only in its later stages that scurvy assumes its more characteristic features. This cachexy annually recurs at St. Petersburg, shortly preceding the vernal equinox. The young, plethoric, and robust are first seized with symptoms of inflammatory fever, which last several days, until suddenly—often in the course of a single night—one of the lower extremities assumes a wax-like hardness, together with a blue appearance, from the effusion of serum, mixed

with the colouring matter of the blood, into the cellular texture of the skin. Under peculiar circumstances, then, might not such an effusion be substituted by a more copious one from the pericardium?

In February 1832, notwithstanding the prevalence of w. and s.w. winds, the thermometer remained stationary under 0', and the epidemic constitution assumed an inflammatory rheumatic character, whilst scurvy was at the same time prevalent. Many instances occurred, not only of pectoral inflammation, but likewise of exudatory pericarditis. A case of the latter is detailed, wherein a more energetic treatment, such as might appear adapted to *acute hydro-pericardia*, led to a successful termination, after about three weeks' illness. The symptoms were here much the same as in the first case, and the diagnosis was confirmed by auscultation with the stethoscope.

About the same period, instances occurred of pericardial exudation *suddenly* supervening upon other affections, and Dr. S. was greatly struck with the following one. A sailor, aged 32, addicted to drinking, and of a lax, bloated habit, entered the hospital on the 30th of February, complaining of pectoral oppression, a humid cough, pains in all his limbs, and in the right hypochondrium. Pulse low and feeble, although not particularly frequent. Temperature of the body natural; tongue furred and discoloured; breath fetid, like that succeeding a debauch. Though appearing to require rest, the patient evinced no real torpor. A solution of the muriate of ammonia with tartarized antimony was administered, and cupping-glasses were applied to the hypochondriac region. After a good night's rest, the patient awoke almost recovered, with the exception of an asthmatic affection, which he declared to be of long standing. The absence of pyrexia, the leucophlegmatic appearance of the patient, the small feeble pulse, and the obtuse sound given by the thorax on percussion, raised the suspicion of a collection of water in the chest, although the patient could lie in any position without inconvenience. He was ordered squills, digitalis, and cream of tartar. The bowels acted spontaneously, and the patient's appetite was very good. Under these circumstances he supped plentifully on the evening of the 22d, and went to bed. Scarcely had he fallen asleep, when he was observed to breathe heavily, and on a sudden to cease breathing altogether. Life had become extinct.

On opening the thorax and abdomen, several pounds of blood flowed away from the two cavities. The right lung partially adhered to the costal pleura, especially towards its inferior lobe, between the extremity of which and the diaphragm a black layer of clotted blood of the size of half a hen's egg was found. The left lung likewise was attached here and there to the costal pleura, but more particularly to the pericardium. The lungs themselves were flaccid, as if macerated. The pericardium contained four pounds of dark blood-coloured fluid without crassamentum. On removing the dark fibrous coat which lined the whole inner surface of the serous membrane, the latter was discovered to be throughout smooth and unimpaired. The heart was enveloped in fat, and compressed into a very small compass; its cavities pressed one against the other, and containing no blood. The jugulars and venæ cavæ were gorged with blood, as were also the vessels of the brain and its sinuses. The liver abounded in blood, and was uncommonly large, but flaccid, retaining the impression of the fingers. The stomach contained the food last taken by the patient, in a perfectly undigested state.

Granting that the pericardium might have contained a small portion of fluid, the deceased's symptoms up to the evening of the 22d appear to Dr. S. wholly disproportionate to the extent of exudation detected after death. He is persuaded that a sudden and copious pericardial discharge succeeded on the patient's falling asleep upon an over-plentiful meal.

At the point of transition from the disease to convalescence, (in the more favorable cases,) the symptoms are usually aggravated to such a degree, that the patients ardently desire to be relieved from their sufferings by death. Nor are the instances frequent where so great a degree of apathy prevails as to render the patient wholly indifferent to his sufferings. An instance is, however, narrated of an almost total paralysis of sensation (so to term it) in a cachetic subject, aged 40. The individual entered the hospital on the 19th of February, with a neglected pleurisy, and was

treated accordingly. On the morning of the 25th, the pleuritic symptoms appeared to have vanished, and the patient considered himself better. New symptoms, however, denoted a change for the worse, and pointed to pericardial effusion. The pulse had become low and feeble, and the pulsation of the heart imperceptible to the hand, and nearly so to the ear. The patient's countenance was pale, sunk, and cold; tongue white, and perfectly chill. He had lain during the whole night in a cold sweat, which his bed and body-linen had thoroughly imbibed. Thus he still lay, on his back, unwilling to move. The pectoral pain had left him, and he could draw a deep breath; even anxiety and oppression seemed gone: in short, the only thing at all complained of was heat, with a constant desire for cold drink, notwithstanding the marble-like coldness of the body's surface. He lingered thus until the morning of the 28th.

The results of the cadaveric inspection proved the diagnosis to have been correct in the above case, both as regards the disease in its original and in its metamorphosed shape. Pleural adhesions, superficial inflammation, and hepatisation of the left lung; redness of the parvagus, on the one hand; on the other, distention of the pericardium with three pounds of discoloured serum, together with all the collateral phenomena peculiar to the disease under notice.

The last cases of pericardial disease, during 1832, occurred in May, and were, with two exceptions, successfully treated by the depletory and derivatory methods, joined to the administration of camphor. Convalescence was usually preceded by copious perspiration.

The influenza which raged at the commencement of 1833 created a general disposition to diseases of the thoracic viscera, and late in spring, a scorbutic tendency was superadded. This combination again brought exudatory pericarditis in its train; the first case originating in inflammation of the anterior mediastinum from external injury, and causing death. Two other fatal cases are worthy of being glanced at, the one merely from its complication with nostalgia, (the subject being a native of Poland,) and with severe hepatic disease; the other from its *appearing* suddenly to supervene on intermittent tertian, on which the exhibition of sulphate of quinine, preceded by that of an emetic, failed to have any effect. In both instances the cause of death was again detected within the pericardium.

The tertian fever, connected with the latter of these cases, was *apparently* the original disorder, but it first seized upon the patient under circumstances wholly unfavorable to the generation of intermittent, refusing *nevertheless* to yield to the usual method of treatment. Dr. S. therefore inclines to the opinion that the fever was here merely a secondary affection, a mask assumed by the pericardial disease, such as is not unfrequently observed in organic disorders of the heart. This view seems strengthened by a case of a similar kind which occurred in February 1834, and in which the intermittent paroxysms yielded to a course of diuretic remedies. During this year (1834) the disease attacked the patients less suddenly, and proved less rapidly fatal. The last case that occurred commenced in July, under general symptoms of scurvy, and terminated fatally on the 53d day by a complication of the exudatory pericarditis with jaundice. Dissection exhibited no very novel feature: the pericardium, however, contained no less than six pounds of fluid. The abdominal organs, though tinged with yellow, were otherwise healthy.

It will be seen from the foregoing cases, that the disease rarely admits of a favorable prognosis being formed: where, however, the malady seized upon the patient suddenly, without any premonitory symptoms, Dr. S. never witnessed an instance of recovery.

Amongst the more striking features of resemblance between the symptoms of the exudatory sanguinolent pericarditis of Dr. Seidnitz and the *passio cardiaca* of Cœlius Aurelianus, several may be inferred from the following passage (cap. 32) in the latter author: "At vero, si jam fuerit præsens passio cardiaca, sequitur ægros articulorum frigidus torpor, aliquando etiam omnium crurum, vel manuum, aut totius corporis: pulsus densus, celer, parvus, imbecillis, &c. attestante hallucinatione, animi desponsione, cum vigilibus jugibus, et quibusdam repentino atque concervato per totum corpus sudore. Quibusdam vero primum cervicæ tenus et vultum, parvus, tenuis, aquætus, dehinc per totum, ut supra diximus,

corpus plurimus, ac tunc crassus et tractuosus atque viscosus vel male redolensrespiratio parva atque anhela et insustentabilis et per morbi progressum rara loquutio ac tremula. Ora pallida, oculi concavi, thoracis gravedo debilitatis causa. Aliquando etiam translatis lingua humecta: aliquibus vero ob complexionem tumoris parvi in visceribus constituti, arida atque sicca, attestante desiderio frigidi potūs. Deficiente ægro, visus obscuritas, articularum livor, unguium uncatio, et *plurimis integer sensus*," &c.

This author appears to have had some intuitive notion of the *real pathological* nature of the disease. Thus (cap. 34), "alii ex corde, alii ex membrana quæ cor circumtegit diaphoresi vexantur, et propterea ii, qui ex membrana cordis solvuntur adjuncto dolore laborant, qui punctionibus crebris ægrum afficit—ii vero, qui ex cordo, gravedinem solum sustinent."

A long and somewhat intricate analysis of Cœlius Aurelianus's opinions, leaves in the mind of Dr. S. no doubt of the identity of the ancient and modern disease. As, generally speaking (he concludes), the scorbutic diathesis has gradually vanished from Southern Europe, and now occurs exclusively in the Northern zones; in like manner, the *cardiac passion* is at this day only to be met with in these latter regions, where scurvy actually rages with no common virulence.

Cœl. Aurelian's assertion: "phlebotomiam nihil jugulatione differre ratio testatur," does not seem to apply to Russia, where the inflammatory tendency of scurvy usually calls for the detraction of blood. Persons in the habit of being bled annually towards the return of spring, are attacked with the incipient symptoms of scurvy if they delay the venesection beyond the usual period. On such occasions, neither spare diet, refrigerents, purgatives, nor, in fact, any method short of phlebotomy, will suffice to reduce the symptoms. Pursuing the consideration of scurvy through its more advanced stages, Dr. S. pronounces the spots first discovered on the lower extremities to be by no means identical with petechiæ, or sугillations beneath the epidermis, but to be owing to extravasation of blood within the cells, where the capillary roots reside. Hence the skin assumes the appearance and feel of goose-skin. In other cases, the malady localizes itself in the second form,—that of extravasation, in large patches, within the cellular texture of the skin and muscles; or in the third form, producing a wax-like induration of the member. In all these cases, the danger to the central organ of circulation is averted, and the fundamental disease advances in its normal development. Again, the heart is safe when the scorbutic affection, without precisely assuming its ordinary form, attacks other internal organs; as, for instance, the spleen, liver, or lungs. Then arise softening of the spleen, appalling jaundices, (which with their concomitant febrile symptoms present the image of true yellow fever,) or *splenisation* of the lungs. The part of the body in which scurvy locates itself, depends partly upon individuality of predisposition, partly, as has been before stated, on the epidemic character of the period.

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On the Use of the Distilled Water of the Prunus Lauro-Cerasus in Facial Neuralgia. By E. S. BENNETT, M.D.

DR. BENNETT, of Charleston in America, relates some cases, in a late number of the American Archives, successfully treated by the remedy here named. It is to be observed, however, that in two out of the three cases described, belladonna was also employed in combination with the cherry-laurel water. The cases were evidently of the neuralgic character, and of considerable standing and severity; and the relief was speedy and permanent. The mode of applying the remedy was to form a lotion of four ounces of the laurel water, one ounce of sulphuric ether, alone, or with half or one drachm of extract of belladonna; and with this lotion the affected parts, previously covered with carded cotton or cotton-wadding, were kept constantly wet. Dr. Bennett says he could give several more cases of similar character and results, but deems these sufficient to test the virtues of the remedy,